

Comparative analysis of emotional intelligence and self-esteem among working and non-working Indian women

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Research Paper

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ABSTRACT

The present study is an attempt to study Emotional Intelligence and Self-esteem among working and non-working women. In this study, some qualitative analysis was done on the sample by asking them to fill up the questionnaires of Emotional Intelligence and Self-esteem. The sample consisted of 150 working women and 150 non-working women. Statistical method applied on the data was t-test along with analysis of standard correlation. The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue) developed by K. V. Petrides, and Rosenberg Self-esteem test developed by Morris Rosenberg. There is a no significant difference between working and non-working women on both Emotional Intelligence and Self-esteem which shows that Working women and non-working women's were same on emotional intelligence and self-esteem.

Introduction

Emotion is the most important thing for every human being when we are talking about emotions there are a variety of emotions we feel in our day-to-day life emotionally intelligent term refers to when humans can manage their emotions and as well others when we talk about others it means the people

around us and how we understand their emotions the term empathy plays an important role in emotional intelligence being able to understand another person

"At the buried core of women's identity is a distinct and vital self, first articulated in childhood, a root identity that gets cut off in the process of growing up female"

in our day-to-day life, many complicated things face we have to manage all things together when we are working we have to manage our job and home at times we have to multitask but when we are not working at that time also we have to manage so many things for our family for our children to make our life satisfied and happy

women play a very important role in every family as daughters mothers and as a wife she manage other's emotions in every particular situation before 1945 when India was not an independent country women were not career oriented their goals were different at that time but they time also women survival in every situation

at that time women were not making their own decisions but still, they knew much better what was best for them so many women contributed their lives to make India independent...

As we know that every women have an different story about her childhood her adulthood her life after marriage and the things she face during working in office every female want to become successful and independent there are many women's who are still face difficulties of managing work life balance

Emotional intelligence to a greater extent is influenced by factors like environment, financial independence, family, and thought process. Considering financial independence, it is usually assumed that career-oriented women are less emotionally inclined than women who take up traditional jobs like homemaking and nursing their children as a full-time engagement

This study aimed at understanding the difference between the emotional intelligence of these two groups, if any, and analyzing the source of these differences.

Review of literature

According to Kumar Dinesh, et al. (2011) working women excelled over non-working women in terms of emotional intelligence and desire for social freedom, and the respondents belonging to high emotional

intelligence group, high desire for social freedom group and working group preferred smaller personal space (PS).

Mayer and Salovey (1997) conducted a study on emotional intelligence, affect, and attitudes. The result of the study was that, despite important exceptions, people are usually motivated to seek pleasant feelings and avoid unpleasant ones. The ability to manage emotions can help people nurture positive affect, avoid being overwhelmed by negative affect, and cope with stress.

Emotional Intelligence among Working and Non-Working Women.Velayudhan, A.;Velayudhan, Kemlit

Emotional Intelligence Of Children Of Working And Non-Working Mothers Dr. Mahmood Ahmad Khan 1 ,Asma Hassan

Kafetsios and Zampetakis (2008) showed that emotional intelligence is an important predictor of job satisfaction. In addition, there was only a significant correlation between job satisfaction and the ability to recognize the emotions of others

. Penrose, Perry and Ball (2007) reviewed on “Emotional Intelligence, teacher self-efficacy and the contribution of teacher status and length of experience”.

PROBLEM OF STUDY

“A Comparative study of Emotional intelligence and self esteem among working and non working women”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of present study are as under:

1. To study Emotional intelligence among working and non working women.
2. To study Self esteem among working and non working women.

- VARIABLES

*In dependent variable: Working and non working women.

*Dependent variable :1] Trait Emotional intelligence questionnaire test
2] Rosenberg Self-esteem test

HYPOTHESES

- 1] Working and nonworking women are the same in their emotional intelligence.
- 2] Working and nonworking women are the same in their self-esteem.

SAMPLE

The sample was drawn from working and non- working women of Kolhapur Thus 150 working and 150 non-working women (housewives) were drawn randomly Age range of women was 25- 35 years.

INSTRUMENT

For collecting data we will use following psychometric tools

- 1] Trait Emotional intelligence questionnaire test

Author: K. V. Petrides,

- 2] Rosenberg Self-esteem test

Author: Morris Rosenberg

STATICALLY ANALYSIS

. As the sample is large, parametric statistical tools were used for analysis. The variances for working and nonworking women on emotional intelligence, self-esteem and stress were equal.

Following statistical tools were used:

1. To test the two study hypotheses independent sample t test was used.
2. To find out correlation between emotional intelligence, self-esteem product moment correlation was used.
3. Simple regression analysis was used with emotional intelligence as independent variable and self-esteem as dependent variable..

- 1] Table showing Mean, SDs and t value of working and nonworking women on Emotional intelligence

Women	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t (Sig.)
Nonworking	150	142.54	12.550	0.598 (NS)
Working	150	141.69	12.180	

NS: Difference is not statistically significant

Hypothesis 1 stated as Working and nonworking women are the same in their emotional intelligences accepted

2] Table showing Mean, SDs and t value of working and nonworking women on self- esteem

Women	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t (Sig.)
Nonworking	150	25.79	3.885	.466 (NS)
Working	150	25.99	3.545	

NS: Difference is not statistically significant

Hypothesis 2 stated as ‘Working and nonworking women are the same in their self-esteem.

’ is accepted

Emotional intelligence is significantly positively correlated with self-esteem of married women.

To examine whether emotional intelligence is significant predictor of self-esteem and stress, simple regression analysis was carried out.

Table showing regression analysis test results

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.449 ^a	.202	.199	3.324

a. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional intelligence

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	831.833	1	831.833	75.282	.000 ^b
	Residual	3292.754	298	11.050		
	Total	4124.587	299			

- a. Dependent Variable: Self-esteem
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional intelligence

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.705	2.220		3.020	.003
	Emotional intelligence	.135	.016	.449	8.677	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Self-esteem

Interpretation: Emotional intelligence significantly predicts self-esteem of married women.

Discussion

The purpose of the study is to compare emotional intelligence and self-esteem of working and nonworking women. Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand ourselves and others' emotions in our day-to-day life we forget about our feelings our felling and our needs and the needs of others when we think about ourselves we forget that another person has the same kind of needs it is not applicable for only working women but non-working too

Self-esteem is “the degree to which the qualities and characteristics contained in one’s self-concept are perceived to be positive. It reflects a person’s physical self-image, view of his or her accomplishments and capabilities, and values and perceived success in living up to them, as well as the ways in which others view and respond to that.

The one person’sself -esteem is not just having a positive mindset or having positive tendencies in another way we do not have the same feelings all the time we are feeling different in different situations self is all about how you feel about yourself in a certain situation or a difficult situation it is about accepting yourself as you are in certain situation

how you define yourself how you see your inner talent your personality and your perception towards yourself

The first research question was working and nonworking women do not differ in their emotional intelligence on emotional intelligence scale so a t-test was applied to find the significant difference

Obtained value of t was 0.598 (NS) whereas table value of mean is 142.54 and 141.69 and standard deviation is 12.550 and 12., the difference was found not statistically significant. Thus, the study shows there is a no significant difference in emotional intelligence between working and non-working women's .

Then the second research question was to find Working and nonworking women do not differ in their self-esteem on self -esteem scale so a t-test was applied to find the significant difference obtained value of t was 466 (NS) whereas table value of Standard deviation is 3.885 and 3.545 whereas value of mean and was 25.79 and 25.99 As the obtained value was same than the table value, the difference was found not to be significant. Thus, the study shows there is no significant difference in self -esteem between working and non-working women's.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded from the study that there is no significant difference between working and non-working women in emotional intelligence and self- esteem emotional intelligence is significantly positively correlated with self-esteem of married women Communicate effectively and empathies with each other play Important role in emotional regulation of women and kindness towards oneself is of utmost importance for both working and non-working women thus the healthy emotions with others and ourselves is very important for making our life mentally healthy and happy.

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